

KEY PRINCIPLES OF KOSTADINOV'S MODELS OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING: IMPLICIT AND EXPLICIT METHODS**Kostadinov O.D.***Ph.D., Guest Lecturer**Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy**Varna, Bulgaria*

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9183-5243

Study in Support of Foreign Language Learning

Abstract

Cognitive processes in learning a foreign language are complex and depend on various emotional and psychological factors. The leading factors are emotional factors that give birth to the desire to learn a foreign language. Psychological factors influence the current state of the human mind. Foreign language information is received through attention via the senses. The most important senses are hearing and vision. Information is acquired through listening and reading, but the human mind possesses greater capabilities. Foreign language information can be received verbally through listening and speaking (in dialogue); listening to an audio recording and reading the accompanying text; and reading an illustrated text with pictures on the subject. Subsequently, the human brain processes the information with attention to assimilate and memorize it. Attention, foreign language perception, and assimilation are crucial factors for memorization, as well as the emotional factors of the learners. All these factors are variable; thus, the cognitive processes should be considered dynamic. The author's thesis is that there is a cycle of psychological factors continuously interacting in cognitive processes. Understanding the dynamics of foreign language cognitive processes helps us to overcome the difficulties in learning it.

Keywords: foreign language cognitive processes; key factors for cognitive processes in foreign language learning; psychological factors attention, interest, curiosity, activation in implicit and explicit foreign language learning.

1. Introduction

People communicate through language. Language has two forms of proficiency: spoken and written. The language used for communication can be either native (L1) or foreign (L2). It is important to note that the mother tongue is acquired in two stages. First, it is learned orally in a family environment, then learned in writing with a teacher. The written acquisition of the language requires a sufficient degree of maturity of the mind, without which it is impossible.

Learning a foreign language can be done in a similar way to learning a native language. Due to the usually advanced age of the learners and the lack of a suitable language environment, in most cases this starts at school or a course with a teacher, where both the spoken and written forms of the language are acquired at the same time. Foreign language acquisition remains an under-researched topic. Over the years, various methods for foreign language learning have been created. Although each methodology sooner or later leads to some degree of success, there is still no definite answer as to which is the most useful.

The present article analyzes the cognitive process of acquiring a foreign language. In this regard, cognitive models were developed considering all the factors on which the acquisition of a foreign language depends. The factors depending on the process of learning a foreign language can be divided into two categories: emotional and psychological. Emotional factors are the motivation and dedication that gives rise to the desire to learn a foreign language. Psychological factors are re-

lated to the process of receiving foreign language information, its perception, assimilation, memorization, and use of the foreign language.

The starting point of the research is the answer to the question of how the native language is learned when spoken in the early childhood years. A characteristic feature is that when the child is born, he does not yet have an active mental activity, nor does he have any idea about the environment. For months, newborns get to know their surroundings and especially their mother, who takes care of them. The first forms of communication with the mother are non-verbal. After certain months, the child begins to express his emotions by making sounds, and with his behavior and facial expressions he makes his first non-verbal communications. During this period, children are not engaged in active activity. Then the children perceive the environment and their relatives, who pass on their language to them, i.e. man's first knowledge is his language, which he acquires spoken thanks to his parents. During this period, children's mental capabilities are not yet well developed, but nevertheless they begin to perceive language and take the first steps in using it. In summary, in their earliest infancy, children are engaged only in self-care, involving entertainment using language. This is the difference between learning one's native language and learning a foreign language at an age when one has one's own concerns and issues to resolve. For these reasons, people are unable to commit themselves solely and entirely to learning a second language. In fact, difficulties in learning a foreign language have subjective and objective causes. The main objective reason for the

difficulties in learning a foreign language in a natural way is the lack of the necessary foreign language environment. Other objective reasons are the commitment of attention to numerous issues and problems, as well as the negative impact of the surrounding environment. All this negatively affects the concentration of the mind and the necessary attention of a person when learning a foreign language. Despite negative conditions, thanks to motivation, internal needs and will, a person can overcome difficulties in learning a foreign language when he knows and realizes their causes.

Foreign language learning requires permanent attention to "reception", "perception", "assimilation" and "memorization" of the studied foreign language. There are two types of attention: deliberate (created by the strong will and efforts of the learner) and natural (created by the learner's desire and interest in the studied foreign language).

Deliberate attention: The learner's attention is created by efforts and commitment to comprehend the studied foreign language.

Natural attention: The learner's attention is created by his or her interest leading to a strong desire and curiosity in the studied foreign language.

Interim conclusion: The acquisition of one's native language occurs implicitly in verbal form, whereas learning the written form of the native language is done explicitly. Foreign languages can be acquired verbally by adolescents through implicit means, but in written form, it requires explicit learning. Key factors in the cognitive processes of foreign language learning have emotional and psychological origins, and they are variable, which directly influence the cognitive process of foreign language learning.

2. Models of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning: Implicit and Explicit Methods

By modelling the cognitive processes involved in implicit and explicit foreign language acquisition, learners and teachers can understand the dynamics of cognitive processes in the human brain and achieve maximum results in Foreign Language Teaching and Learning, which is a two-sided process, akin to a coin.

2.1. Implicit Model of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning

The model includes a chain of 8 sequentially connected factors and 4 internal mind processes, all united in 3 interconnected groups (blocks) of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning. (table 1)

Table 1

Kostadinov's Model of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning by Adolescents: Implicit Methods		
Motivation and exposure	Psycho-factors	Acquisition
1. Strength of motivation	5. Input interaction	9. Perception
2. Type of language exposure: a) listening to foreign radio and watching TV, also reading b) living and working alone in a foreign language environment	6. Sensor reception: a) by listening to live speech b) by listening and reading	10. Assimilation by: comprehension, understanding in context by listening and reading
3. Level of language exposure: a) linguistic environment b) immersion environment	7. Concentration: a) by will b) by curiosity	11. Memorization: unconsciously and effortlessly
4. Time of language exposure: a) non-intensive b) intensive	8. Attention: a) deliberate b) natural	12. Knowledge: a) passive b) active
Author: Ognyan Kostadinov, ORCID ID. No: 0000-0002-9183-5243		

❖ **Motivation and exposure** represent a group of factors related to the motivation of the foreign language learner, as well as the type, level, and duration of the acquired foreign language knowledge. These factors are variable within certain frameworks and arranged in a logical sequence and importance. The special thing about variable factors is that they have different strengths and impacts on learning a foreign language.

• **Motivation** – motivation is a generalizing concept and includes various reasons for its occurrence. These reasons can be graded in strength, which is why motivation depending on the reasons for its existence

can also be relatively commensurate. Examples of motivation for learning a foreign language graded by strength:

- Desire to understand or communicate in a foreign language.
- Travel and familiarization with foreign cultures.
- Professional opportunities available to those who speak a foreign language.
- Academic goals requiring mastery of the foreign language.
- Internal development and self-confidence.
- Internal need of the person

- **Type of language exposure** - has the following sub-factors:

- listening to foreign radio and watching TV, also reading.

- living and working alone in a foreign language environment.

- **Level of language exposure** - has the following sub-factors:

- linguistic environment.

- language immersion environment.

- **Time of language exposure** - has the following sub-factors:

- non-intensive

- intensive language exposure

All these factors have a greater or lesser stimulating effect. The improvement of the stimulating factors depends on the learners and their opportunities to provide a more suitable language environment where they can most easily and quickly acquire the spoken foreign language.

The most important factor in this group for achieving a quick and good result is the last one: Time of language exposure, with the "intensive" sub-factor. The time the learner actively uses for Implicit Foreign Language Learning is of crucial importance.

❖ **Psycho-factors** represent a group of factors related to the mental process in foreign language acquisition. These factors are variable within certain frameworks and arranged in a logical sequence and importance. The special thing about variable factors is that they have different strengths and impacts on learning a foreign language. Some of the factors have sub-factors, for example:

- **Sensor reception** - has the following sub-factors:

- Reception of verbal information by listening to live speech.

- Reception of verbal and written information by listening to live speech and reading a text

- **Concentration** - has the following sub-factors:

- It could be by "will", or

- It could be by "curiosity".

- **Attention**

Robinson, P., Mackey, A., Gas, S., Schmidt, R., (2012) Attention and awareness play a crucial role in second language acquisition (SLA), particularly in the implicit method. Implicit learning, which occurs without conscious awareness, has been a subject of debate in cognitive psychology and SLA research. This method emphasizes exposure to language input without explicit instruction, allowing learners to acquire language skills intuitively. Research suggests that implicit learning relies on attention to linguistic input and the subsequent processing of this input, leading to the formation of implicit knowledge. While explicit knowledge can become implicit through practice, attentional mechanisms regulate the acquisition and storage of implicit language knowledge. Studies in cognitive science have shown that attention directs learners' focus to specific aspects of language input, facilitating the acquisition of language skills. Attention and awareness

are integral components of the implicit method, shaping learners' language learning experiences and influencing their language proficiency development over time.[1]

Attention has the following sub-factors:

- deliberate

- natural

Attention is an important psychological factor. Attention can be deliberate and natural. Natural attention has a stronger effect on the foreign language learning process.

❖ **Acquisition** represents a group of factors related to the processing and memorization of the received foreign language information, before its transformation into knowledge.

- **Perception:** *Besedova, P., Veriskova, V., (2020), Perception belongs to the complex and complicated psychic procedures actively participating in a certain reality construction. Perception of foreign languages is a very complicated phenomenon, which has sensory character and can act with only two senses presented - hearing and vision. Such perception character is based on an ability to integrate the hearing sound firmly into the category of a certain phoneme without letting it.*[2]

- **Assimilation:** In foreign language learning, assimilation occurs implicitly through listening and reading comprehension, unconsciously and effortlessly.

- **Memorization:**

Francis, V. (2023) To learn another language effectively, it's crucial to memorize not just individual words, but complete sentences. Memorizing isolated words and then attempting to arrange them into coherent sentences is tedious and inefficient. Our brains are wired to store information with context, making full sentences much more valuable as they provide meaning and exemplify how words are used in context. This method mirrors the natural process our brains undergo when learning our native language, allowing for a more intuitive acquisition of grammar without the need to learn explicitly grammatical rules. While initially daunting, learning sentences in a foreign language is essential as language usage revolves around speaking sentences rather than isolated words. Through sufficient practice, these sentences become ingrained in memory, facilitating faster language mastery. This implicit approach to foreign language learning emphasizes the importance of context-rich learning and effective retention techniques for enhanced language acquisition.[3]

Memorization in the implicit method is unconscious and effortless.

All main processes in the human mind are important, but memorization is crucial because it pre-determines knowledge.

❖ **Knowledge** – as a final product, which could be a long-term element of human memory, but on the other hand, it is also a variable element of the foreign language cognitive process. Language knowledge could be passive (or receptive) and active (or productive). In implicit learning grammar, rules are not studied but acquired unconsciously through grammar patterns and expressions.

2.2. Explicit Model of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning

The model includes a chain of 8 sequentially connected factors and 4 internal mind processes, all united

in 3 interconnected groups (blocks) of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning. (tab. 2)

Table 2

Kostadinov's Model of Cognitive Processes in Foreign Language Learning by Adolescents: Explicit Methods		
Emotional factors	Psycho-factors	Acquisition
1. Motivation	5. Input interaction	9. Perception
2. Objective: a) material incentive b) spiritual incentive	6. Sensor reception by: a) listening b) listening and reading	10. Assimilation: a) consciously b) unconsciously
3. Dedication: a) by commitment b) by conviction	7. Concentration: a) by will b) by curiosity	11. Memorization: a) consciously b) unconsciously
4. Personal feelings: a) desire b) passion	8. Attention: a) deliberate b) natural	12. Knowledge: a) receptive b) productive
Author: Ognyan Kostadinov, ORCID ID. No: 0000-0002-9183-5243		

❖ **Emotional factors** – are divided into four categories, each of which is defined within a framework of variables.

- **Motivation:** Lapadat, L., Lapadat, M., (2023) Motivation is a complex construct that can be influenced by various factors, such as personality, cultural background, social environment, and personal experiences. Language teachers need to recognize the importance of motivation in foreign language learning and incorporate motivational strategies into their teaching practices.[3]

- **Objective:**

- Material incentive: usually, it is a necessity for professional advancement.

- Spiritual incentive: typically, it is a desire to learn a foreign language.

- **Dedication:**

- A commitment originating from some engagement or decision.

- By conviction originating from some belief or confidence.

- **Personal feelings:**

- A strong desire (a strong preference for a foreign language).

- Passion (a strong and motivated preference for a foreign language, often related to something personal).

- ❖ **Psycho-factors**

- **Input interaction** - the process through which input information is processed through interaction with psychological factors.

- **Sensor reception:**

- by listening to live speech

- by listening and reading

- **Concentration:**

- by willingness to pay attention to what the listener (or reader) is hearing or reading (it is through dedication).

- by curiosity about what the listener (or reader) is hearing or reading (it is natural).

- **Attention:**

Robinson, P., Mackey, A., Gas, S., Schmidt, R., (2012) In contrast to the implicit method, the explicit method in second language acquisition (SLA) emphasizes conscious learning and explicit instruction. Attention and awareness are essential components of the explicit method, as learners actively engage with language input through focused attention and deliberate processing. Explicit learning involves the explicit acquisition of linguistic rules and structures, often through formal instruction and explicit explanation. Research in cognitive psychology and SLA has explored the role of attention in explicit learning, highlighting its importance in directing learners' focus to specific language features and facilitating the acquisition of explicit language knowledge. Awareness of language forms and structures is heightened in the explicit method, as learners consciously attend to linguistic input and actively seek to understand and internalize language rules. While explicit learning may initially rely on conscious effort and attention, repeated practice and exposure can lead to the automatization of explicit knowledge, enabling learners to use language more fluently and accurately over time. Attention and awareness are central to the explicit method, guiding learners' language learning processes and contributing to their overall language proficiency development.[1]

- Deliberate listening or reading
- Naturally paying attention to what is being heard or read.

❖ **Acquisition** - refers to a collection of characteristics associated with the processing and memory of information acquired in a foreign language, prior to the information being transformed into knowledge.

- **Perception:** Zhou, J. (2018) Language perception is a crucial concept involving speech perception, understanding, and beholding. It is concerned with language development and speech production. Humboldt and Sapir (1985) believed that language is an audio-semiotic system, with auditory sense and perception in speech being the key aspects. Some scholars define language perception as "words' sensory feelings," while others view it as a process of cognitive and aesthetic activity initiated from language words. Pan (1995) proposed that language perception is a complex psychological and epistemic activity caused by language words, including feeling, intuition, memory, and thinking. Hu (1992) emphasized that language perception is a synthesis of intuitive, fixed, and dynamic constituents, regulating speech practice.[4]

- **Assimilation** – In foreign language learning, explicitly, assimilation occurs through learning grammar rules and doing grammar exercises. It is a conscious way of acquiring a foreign language by studying with an effort to understand the content of the material.

- **Memorization**

Francis, V. (2023) Human brains are highly efficient at memorizing information, but this doesn't always happen most effectively. They are designed to remember important things for survival, such as the location of food. To learn a foreign language effectively, we need to use methods that correspond to the way our brains memorize information. This includes effective techniques for encoding, storage, and retrieval of information. If we cannot retrieve the information we have memorized, we cannot use it.[5]

There are two types of memorizations:

- Conscious memorization of foreign words and grammar rules.
- Unconscious memorization of foreign words and grammar patterns.

❖ **Knowledge** – as a final product, which could be a long-term element of human memory, but on the other hand, it is also a variable element of the foreign language cognitive process. Language knowledge can be passive (also known as receptive) and active (also

known as productive). In explicit methods, grammar rules and language structure are consciously studied. Along with explicit language instruction, learners also unconsciously acquire some knowledge implicitly.

3. The Dynamic Duo of Attention and Curiosity in Kostadinov's Cognitive Models

Cognitive processes in foreign language learning are emotional and psychological, depending on many factors. The impact of these factors on cognitive processes directly influences the result of learning. The most important psychological factor is attention. The role of human attention in learning processes is vital, that's why raising attention must be the priority during the acquisition of a foreign language. There are two main ways to boost human attention: naturally and deliberately. The natural way is an emotional way of attracting the learner's curiosity about the studied material. The deliberate way of raising attention depends on the learner who must use his own will to do it. There is also a third way to increase attention through suggestive methods. Foreign language learning could be used in all ways to attract learners' attention, but the best is to use natural ways of raising attention. Foreign language learners' attention could be attracted in two ways: by curiosity related to the grammar unit, which is currently studied, and by the contents of text used to show this unit. Human curiosity about certain subjects and interest in the content of some audio or written text could be described as an incentive to start a cognitive process of foreign language learning.

The relationship between attention and interest is closely related and important to our learning, engagement, and development. Attention is the ability to focus on a particular aspect of the environment, while interest is a state of curiosity and enjoyment that motivates us to learn and explore. Attention is a gateway to deeper engagement, allowing us to immerse ourselves in a subject, while interest sustains attention through intrinsic motivation and satisfaction from learning. Cultivating interest through personalization, variety, goal setting, and active learning can improve our ability to focus, learn more effectively, and derive greater satisfaction from our efforts.

❖ Kostadinov's Model for activating and keeping foreign language learners' attention.

A cycle of four factors continuously interacting in cognitive processes: Attention – Interest – Curiosity – Activation

Kostadinov's Model for activating and keeping foreign language learners' attention

Author: Ognyan Kostadinov, ORCID ID. No: 0000-0002-9183-5243

Figure 1

Kostadinov's Model for activating and keeping foreign language learners' (fig.1) attention operates as a circular process consisting of four interconnected factors. The model begins with "Attention", the initial focal point of the learner's cognitive engagement. This attention is then fueled by "Interest", a state of curiosity and enjoyment that motivates the learner to explore and engage further. As interest deepens, it naturally leads to "Curiosity", prompting the learner to seek out more information and experiences related to the language being learned. This curiosity, in turn, triggers "Activation", where the learner actively participates in language activities, exercises, or interactions, reinforcing their attention and starting the cycle anew. Each component of the model interacts seamlessly with the others, creating a continuous loop of cognitive engagement that is essential for effective foreign language learning.

Conclusion: The cognitive processes involved in learning a foreign language are multifaceted and dynamic, influenced by emotional and psychological factors. Emotional factors, such as motivation and conviction, ignite the desire to learn a foreign language, while psychological factors, including attention, perception, assimilation, and memorization, shape the process of acquiring language skills.

Understanding the parallels between the acquisition of one's native language and learning a foreign language sheds light on the challenges faced by learners. While native language acquisition occurs implicitly through immersion in a linguistic environment from infancy, learning a foreign language often necessitates

explicit effort due to the absence of such an environment. However, both implicit and explicit methods of learning involve complex cognitive processes, where attention plays a crucial role.

Models of cognitive processes in foreign language learning distinguish between implicit and explicit methods, each comprising interconnected factors. Implicit learning relies on motivation, exposure, psycho-factors, and acquisition, while explicit learning incorporates emotions, psycho-factors, and acquisition. Regardless of the method, attention emerges as a pivotal psychological factor, with natural attention driven by curiosity proving particularly effective in enhancing learning outcomes.

Kostadinov's model emphasizes the cyclical nature of attention, interest, curiosity, and activation in sustaining cognitive engagement during foreign language learning. This dynamic interplay underscores the importance of fostering intrinsic motivation and personal interest to facilitate effective language acquisition.

In conclusion, a comprehensive understanding of the emotional and psychological dimensions of cognitive processes in foreign language learning is essential for overcoming challenges and optimizing learning outcomes. By recognizing the intricate interplay of factors such as attention, motivation, and curiosity, educators and learners can devise strategies to enhance language acquisition and proficiency.

References

1. Robinson, P., Mackey, A., Gas, S., Schmidt, R. (2012), Attention and awareness in second language acquisition, *The Routledge Handbook of Second Language Acquisition*, Routledge, New York, ISBN: 978-0-203-80818-4 (ebk), pp. 247-267
2. Besedova, P., Veriskova, V., (2020), FOREIGN LANGUAGE PERCEPTION OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS OF MUSIC AND FOREIGN LANGUAGES, International Conference on Education & Educational Sciences EpICEEPSY, e-ISSN: 2672-8141, DOI: 10.15405/epiceepsy.20111.16
3. Lapadat, L., Lapadat, M., (2023), The importance of Motivation in Foreign Language Learning, Scientific Bulletin of the Politehnica University of Timisoara, Vol.22, Issue 1/2023, DOI: 10.59168/VGLE2734
4. Zhou, J. (2018), The Macroscopic Analysis of Language Percept, *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 232, 4th International Conference on Arts, Design and Contemporary Education (ICADCE 2018), Atlantic Press
5. Francis., V. (2023) How to Memorize Words in Another Language, Taal hammer, Available on: <https://www.taalhammer.com/how-to-memorize-words-in-another-language/>.